

EBFMC25-OP-67 · Multidisciplinary Approach and Integrated Care for an Immobile Homeless Patient with Impaired Consciousness and Malnutrition

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Neurological disorders and cognitive impairments resulting from chronic alcohol use significantly reduce the quality of life, especially among homeless individuals (Sahu, Verma, & Bhaskar, 2025; Stone, Dowling, & Cameron, 2019). In this vulnerable group, where physical, nutritional, and psychosocial problems overlap, a comprehensive and holistic approach is essential (Klop et al., 2018). This case report presents the multidisciplinary management and integrated care process of a homeless, immobile male patient with impaired consciousness and malnutrition, followed up in a palliative care unit affiliated with a family medicine department. The case also emphasizes the positive outcomes achieved through the biopsychosocial model, a fundamental principle in family medicine (Molina, 1983).

Case Presentation: A 45-year-old homeless male with a history of chronic alcoholism, no known comorbidities, and no family support was admitted to the emergency department with impaired consciousness. After initial stabilization in the ICU, he was transferred to the family medicine-based palliative care unit. On admission, his Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) was 11 (E3M5V3), muscle strength was 2/5 in the lower extremities, and laboratory results revealed hypoalbuminemia and anemia. A biopsychosocial care plan was implemented, including a nutritional regimen of 2500 kcal/day, vitamin supplementation, physiotherapy, pain and symptom management, and preventive care for pressure ulcers. Social services initiated a search for family contact and long-term care planning.

Discussion: The patient's clinical condition improved significantly during the follow-up: consciousness level increased to GCS 15, pain decreased, communication improved, and he gradually regained mobility. At discharge, he was able to walk without assistance. Due to the lack of familial support, institutional placement was arranged in coordination with the social services unit.

Conclusion: This case illustrates how palliative care, when guided by the biopsychosocial model within a family medicine framework, can promote not only symptom control but also functional recovery and enhanced quality of life. Early integration of social services is essential for discharge planning and the success of integrated care practices in vulnerable populations.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Family medicine, integrated care, palliative care, biopsychosocial approach

INTRODUCTION

Neurological disorders and cognitive impairments caused by chronic alcohol use can lead to significant disability and decreased quality of life, particularly among homeless individuals (Sahu, Verma, & Bhaskar, 2025; Stone, Dowling, & Cameron, 2019). Homeless patients with alcohol dependency are at higher risk of morbidity and mortality at younger ages compared to the general population, due to complex physical and psychosocial problems (Gaber et al., 2024).

Palliative care practices aim to improve quality of life through a holistic approach that addresses multifaceted issues such as pain and malnutrition (Barawid et al., 2015; Wittry et al., 2018). In Turkey, palliative care services have been developing in recent years, and multidisciplinary palliative care approaches have played a critical role in achieving a state of “well-being” in patients (Can, 2023). The integrated care model, which has recently gained attention, seeks to ensure that the patient centered care model is carried out in a coordinated and continuous manner across hospital, home, and institutional care settings (Koehler et al., 2020). In this study, we present the multidisciplinary approach and integrated care process provided at a palliative care center for an immobile homeless case admitted with impaired consciousness and malnutrition.

CASE PRESENTATION

A 45-year-old male homeless patient, with a history of chronic alcoholism and no other comorbidities, was initially admitted to the anesthesia intensive care unit from the emergency department due to altered consciousness. He was then transferred to the palliative care center with diagnoses of impaired consciousness, malnutrition, and immobility. At the time of admission, his vital signs were stable. On physical examination, he was unconscious, disoriented, and uncooperative. His Glasgow Coma Scale (GCS) score was 11 (E3M5V3). Neurological examination revealed responses with meaningless sounds. The patient was immobile, with a muscle strength of 2/5 in the lower extremities. Laboratory results showed negative acute phase reactants and elevated ALT and AST levels. Albumin and hemoglobin levels were found to be low. It was learned that the patient had no known relatives. Due to inadequate oral intake, a dietary consultation was requested, and a nutritional support plan providing 2500 kcal/day was initiated.

A stage 1 pressure ulcer measuring 2 cm × 2 cm was observed on the sacral region. Regular repositioning and a preventive care approach were implemented with the assistance of clinical support staff, along with pain palliation. Given the patient's history of chronic alcoholism, investigations for Wernicke's encephalopathy and hepatic failure were conducted. Vitamin supplementation was provided, and nutritional support, pain palliation, and physiotherapy sessions were continued. During this period, social workers attempted to contact the patient's relatives.

During palliative care service follow-up, it was observed that the patient's consciousness improved; he was able to form complex sentences, his pain had decreased, and his facial expressions became more relaxed. Although he was immobile upon admission, he began mobilization with a walker during his stay in the unit, and by the time of discharge, he was able to walk without the need for a walker.

By the end of the palliative care process, the patient showed significant improvements in consciousness and nutritional status (E4M6V5), and effective pain and symptom management was achieved.

Due to the inability to reach his relatives and his status as homeless, although his overall condition had improved, institutional placement was arranged. Following the completion of reporting and consultations regarding follow-up in institutional care settings, he was placed in a care facility under the coordination of the social services unit.

DISCUSSION

In our palliative care unit, a multidisciplinary team composed of physicians, nurses, physiotherapists, nutritionists, and social workers collaborates in patient management (Barawid et al., 2015; Wittry et al., 2018). The multidisciplinary teamwork conducted in the palliative care center, guided by the biopsychosocial approach that is fundamental in family medicine, contributes significantly to improving the quality of life of patients (Molina, 1983).

CONCLUSION

This case demonstrates that physiological stabilization can be achieved through palliative care and that individuals can attain a state of well-being through effective pain and symptom management (Teoli, Schoo, & Kalish, 2025).

In terms of integrated care practices, it is crucial that social service units initiate placement planning into institutional care settings, if necessary, from the early stages of hospitalization in order to ensure a well-structured discharge process (Koehler et al., 2020). Palliative care practices not only address end-of-life care but also focus on the management of chronic illnesses by alleviating symptom burden, enhancing patient functionality, and supporting access to social support networks (Klop et al., 2018; Teoli, Schoo, & Kalish, 2025).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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